

Teratogenic Effect of Different Drugs at Different Stages in Pregnancy

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Abstract:- Because of the potential for teratogenic medication effects on the foetus, treating common ailments during pregnancy is challenging. The first eight weeks of human development are referred to as the embryogenesis period, sometimes known as the organogenesis period. Such a deficiency is caused by a teratogenic agent, which are compounds that could harm the human embryo or foetus physically or functionally. An acknowledgment of the tragedies caused by the thalidomide epidemic in the 1970s and the rubella epidemic in the early 1960s in the field of teratology. Chloramphenicol, Warfarin, Valproate, and Thalidomide are a few of the medications that might cause abnormalities such microcephaly, hydrocephalus, spina bifida, and a number of other syndromes. Many of these substances can enter human tissue and a developing foetus, which can have detrimental effects on the human reproductive health. Numerous biological and physical elements, like as radiation and infection, contribute to teratogenic effects.

Keywords:- Teratogenic, Teratogenicity, Birth Defects, Pregnancy, Early Pregnancy, Miscarriage, Stillbirth, Preterm Birth, Congenital abnormalities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the risk of teratogenic consequences from the drug and physiologic changes in the mother as a result of the pregnancy, drug therapy presents a specific concern during pregnancy [1,7]. When a sperm enters an egg, pregnancy happens. This process, known as fertilisation, often takes place in the fallopian tube of the female. The fertilised egg starts to divide right away, creating a huge mass of cells. The fertilised egg implants into the uterine wall between 5-7 days after ovulation and begins to create the placenta [2]. The first eight weeks of pregnancy are primarily when medications have an impact on how the human embryo develops. The blastocyst is free to move around in the uterus for the first week and relies on uterine secretion for sustenance. At this point, it is unknown if exogenous factors like medications can result in congenital abnormalities, but they can cause the embryo's death [3]. A, B, C, D, or X risk categories were created by the FDA to indicate a drug's potential to cause birth defects if used during pregnancy in 1979 [5]. The formation of deformities in the foetus is referred to as teratogenic. A teratogenic drug causes such a defect. The term "teratogen" is typically used to describe chemicals that impede the normal anatomical development of an embryo [4].

II. STAGES OF PREGNANCY

➤ First trimester: - 1 to 3 Months (week1 through 12)

The first trimester lasts 12 weeks and starts at fertilisation. Pregnancy usually goes like way for the first three months. During this trimester, the fertilised egg will grow from a small group of cells into a foetus that is beginning to exhibit human characteristics [3]. Although the first trimester is delightful, the majority of people also go through this time with painful symptoms including fatigue and morning sickness [5].

➤ Second trimester: - 4 to 7 Months (weeks13 through 28)

The second trimester of pregnancy is usually viewed as the best part. By this time, any morning sickness should have passed, along with any discomfort from the early stages of pregnancy. You may also start to feel movement when the foetus flips and spins inside your uterus. [1].

➤ Third trimester: - 8 to 10 Months (weeks29 through 40)

The last stage of your pregnancy is this. Avoid the temptation to start counting down the days until your due date in the hopes that it will arrive early by resisting the urge. With each week of this final period of development, the foetus prepares for birth. During the third trimester, the foetus gains weight quickly and gains body fat that will be advantageous after birth [6].

III. RISK OF TERATOGENICITY OF DRUGS USED IN PREGNANCY

➤ Antiepileptic drugs:

AEDs have been suspected as having teratogenic potential since the 1960s. Most WWE cannot afford to stop using AEDs because seizures pose a risk of harm or perhaps death [10]. Anti-epileptic medications increase the likelihood of conceiving a kid with congenital abnormalities more than the general population [3]. AED use during the first trimester of pregnancy may increase the likelihood that children delivered to WWE (Well Women Exam) women will require medical countermeasures [10].

➤ Analgesics and Anti-inflammatory Drugs:

Acetaminophen and Propoxyphene are reasonable choice when symptomatic relief of pain is required. Acetylsalicylic acid has probably more widely used in pregnancy but high doses may cause intrauterine growth retardation. Propoxyphene has not been associated with teratogenic effects, but codeine has been related to congenital abnormalities in the respiratory system [3].

➤ *Antidepressants and Anxiolytics Drugs:*

Clinical experience has shown that pregnant women exposed to antidepressants experience greater spontaneous abortions and stillbirths. Poor Neonatal Adaptation (PNA) is more common when pregnant women receive treatment in the third trimester [11]. Diazepam (Valium) use during pregnancy has been linked in certain studies to birth malformations include cleft lip, heart issues, and pyloric stenosis [3]. Due to the possibility of congenital malformations, lithium should be avoided during pregnancy [3].

➤ *Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin:*

Levofloxacin and Cipro are examples of other antibiotics. These medications may impair the baby's skeletal and muscular development as well as the mother's joints and possibly even cause nerve damage [21].

IV. HOW DO DRUGS CROSS THE PLACENTA

- Most drugs can cross the placenta by passive diffusion
- Placental membrane is semi-permeable
- Movement of drugs through the placenta is limited by a single layer of trophoblast [31].

V. TERATOGENESIS AND FDA CLASSIFICATION DRUG

➤ *Teratogenesis*

Congenital abnormalities of the foetus occur. These are compounds that, when exposed to an embryo or foetus, can poison them and result in lifelong birth abnormalities. (Mistakes in functionality or structure) [31].

Table 1 FDA Classification Drugs

Category	Characteristics	Examples
A	The foetus in the first trimester of pregnancy is not at risk, according to adequate and controlled research conducted in women.	Folic acid Thyroxine
B	There are no controlled trials in pregnant women, despite animal reproductive research failing to show a risk to the foetus	Paracetamol Erythromycin
C	Only if the potential benefits outweigh the potential risks to the foetus should drugs be given, regardless of whether studies in animals have demonstrated a harmful effect on the foetus (teratogenic, embryocidal, or other).	Morphine
D	Based on data from studies on adverse reactions, there is strong evidence that there is a danger to the human foetus, although the benefits of using the medicine while pregnant may outweigh the risks.	Antiepileptics
X	Proven foetal abnormalities in animal and human studies. Drugs should only be administered if the possible advantages outweigh the potential hazards to the foetus [2].	Thalidomide Sedative

VI. TERATOGENESIS OF DRUGS AT STAGES

Table 2 First Trimester

FIRST TRIMESTER	
Thalidomide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phocomelia: - Absence of organ, one or more limbs and is denoted a terminal transverse defect. ▪ Shortened or absent long bones of the limbs
Phenytoin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Foetal Hydantoin Syndrome ▪ Nail and digital hypoplasia ▪ Oral cleft (cleft lip and palate)
Alcohol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Foetal Alcohol Syndrome ▪ CVS abnormalities ▪ CNS abnormalities
Tetracycline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Permanent teeth staining ▪ Discoloration and hypoplasia ▪ Caries and pigmentation of permanent teeth
Corticosteroids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cleft lip and palate

Warfarin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Hypoplasia of nasal bridge ▪ CNS malformation ▪ Anticoagulant
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Table 3 The Second and Third Trimester

THE SECOND AND THIRD TRIMESTER	
Chloramphenicol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gray baby syndrome
Propranolol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bradycardia ▪ Neonatal hypoglycaemia ▪ Poor uterine blood flow
NSAIDs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prostaglandin synthesis inhibitors ▪ Increase risk for postpartum haemorrhage
ACE inhibitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Renal damage
Antithyroids	Risk for neonatal hypothyroidism and goitres (Methimazole, Carbimazole, Iodide and Propylthiouracil)
Chloramphenicol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gray baby syndrome

VII. CONCLUSION

The study's analysis of this literature demonstrates that worries about medication use during pregnancy are not limited to the possibility of delivering a kid with a congenital birth defect. Despite the fact that pregnant women exaggerate the teratogenic risk of medicine usage, the majority of the drugs were thought to carry relatively modest risks and substantial rewards. This can be considered by medical professionals when counselling expectant ladies. From the literature, we isolated six key teratogenic pathways related to the use of medical drugs. Numerous other prescription and over-the-counter medications may also promote tumorigenesis through these mechanisms, in addition to the fact that nearly all medicinal pharmaceuticals recognised by Schwarz et al. (2007) as U.S. FDA class X are associated to at least one of these processes. some prescription drugs

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